

October 5-9, 2020

10:00 - 11:30	Session 9: Synergies with Wavelengths & Facilities	Chair: Andreea Petric (STScI)
10:00 - 10:30	9a Invited Talk: Ranga-Ram Chary (IPAC)	Unsolved issues in Galaxy Evolution at the Epoch of Reionization
10:30 - 10:45	9b Manda Banerji (Univ of Southampton)	Galaxies Science with the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space Time (LSST): The Need for Infra-red Data
10:45 - 11:00	9c Lucia Pozzetti (INAF-Bologna)	Galaxy formation and evolution in the era of Euclid
11:00 - 11:15	9d Lukas Zalesky (IoA)	The Hawaii Twenty Square Degree Survey: Synergy with Next Generation Space Telescopes
11:15 - 11:30	9e Adam Muzzin (York)	Resolving Problems in Galaxy Formation with HST, WFIRST and GIRMOS
11:30 - 12:00	9f Brant Robertson (UCSC)	SIT Talk

Session 9 live captioning on Friday, 9 October 2020

Good morning everyone. welcome to day 5, session 9 of the *Galaxy Formation and Evolution in the Era of the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope* conference. Before we start, a few reminders. We have put up content for this conference on slack, and we expect everybody to read and abide by it. We have a survey which is also on the announcement channel, which we would like to know how it was experienced this week and this virtual conference. if you can fill that out, it will take 3 minutes only and if you can fill it out as soon as possible when the meeting is fresh in your mind, that would be very helpful. but at least by 16th of october if you can put it out, that would be great. Another reminder is that for the speakers, if you are comfortable with sharing your slides then you should upload them to your respective channels, the main channels, not the question and a subtext because when you post in the main channel everyone will get the indication that there is something new on that channel. again, we will use slack for question and answers. for this session, you will be using session 9 and you will use individual speakers threads to ask questions. we have posters on slack, you can start if you haven't at the i poster links channel where all the posters are listed and you can then go to the individual poster channels and interact with presenters. and just to let you know, this is the last day of the conference but the slack will be open for a few months i would guess, starting from next week so feel free to use it. use it for posters, use it to upload, use it to ask questions. So with that, I will hand it over to **Andreea Petric**, chair of the session.

Thank you, many thanks to the organizers for a fantastic conference given the difficulties of online conferencing. So today session, I have the pleasure to -- the pleasure in this session on synergy between the roman telescope with instruments at various wavelengths in various places around the world, so we will have the pleasure of six talks. two of which are invited at the end and the beginning of the session and they will talk 25 minutes, i will give you a warning after 20 when you have 5 minutes remaining. The other talks are contributed talks are i will give you a warning after 10 minutes. If we do encounter technical difficulties, we will try to move on to the next talk and come back depending.

so with no further ado, it is my pleasure to introduce the first speaker of the session. **Ranga-Ram Chary** from IPAC, who will tell us about unresolved issues in galaxy evolution. Take it away, please share your slides.

Ranga: Great. so, thanks very much to the organizers for giving me an opportunity to share a few talks on synergy's and what problems they are going to solve and galaxy evolution. it's a little bit like looking into a crystal ball, in the era of roman which will be launched in 2025 i have to predict what problems we currently have that will remain unsolved especially after a few years and a few years of euclid. and if you years of the large telescopes. the way i structured this talk is highlighted the problems that exist and the wavelength that which we will use to try to address those problems. of course the background in this slide is no surprise, because it's not just to brighten your morning but it's really to highlight multi-wavelength information and absolutely crucial to get a complete picture of galaxy evolution. so, this slide is going to be a summary and this is essentially for graduate students and young energetic postdocs who are looking to build a career in galaxy evolution. and in my opinion, these are what issues we have learned and what we would like to learn going into the future. so i'm going to talk on these topics, this is just a high-level summary of this. the first thing is the bright end of the galaxy greater than 6 at cosmic times every billion years and earlier. it's dependency on environment. also we've made a lot of progress thanks to some very nice surveys, we desperately need spectroscopic confirmation. and the real reason we want this is the galaxy luminosity function ever matches the dark matter halo mass function, because that defies the role of feedback at the bright end, it's thought to be feedback. at the faint end it's thought to be stellar feedback, supernova. this next question we would like to get a better handle on is surface brightness limitation, we have these ultradeep surveys with hst that have shed a lot of light on what the function is doing, but the key questions we are underestimating the at the faint end of the luminosity function. the flux that you see in hst versus ground-based in the same galaxy tends to be half. so there are other sources that we are missing one may calculate the luminosity function. people do a lot of spectroscopy, we tried to do simulations to correct for this but it's obviously a function of size and what the surface brightness distribution is and we would like to have a better handle on this. is there really a plateau in a star formation rate which is star formation rate divided by stellar mass with increasing red shift? we know the specific star formation rate increases with red shift, and then it starts to flatten. is there really a plateau or is there something we don't understand about star formation? we are also finding extreme the unusual nebular emission line strengths in hydrogen galaxies and what it implies in terms of biomass evolution is definitely an unsolved problem. we like to understand how these galaxies grow, by which i mean are they growing through cold gas accretion or starbursts? we would like to know more about their dust content which we typically probe using uv slopes, spectroscopy. we have this weird buy modality, there seems to be some sources which are bright but other sources which are very similar masses which are completely undetected. and i don't have a clear understanding of why this is. we'd also like to know what the agn content is in these hydrogen galaxies, and where the supermassive black holes come from. and we like to understand the population of x-ray boundaries in them, which may be low mass black holes which came out of supermassive stars that are powering the star formation in these galaxies. and that of course requires very deep x-ray surveys. and the basic question would like to answer is the slope of the black hole stellar mass relationship different? and finally, because we should not ignore the most difficult, which are gamma rays. can we reconcile burst rates with the star formation rate with blank field surveys? that's something that is uncertain, uncertainty in grp production mechanisms, and the aforementioned uncertainties in star formation rates in blank field surveys. so let's talk about these in more detail. so we all know how we detect hydrogen galaxies, but just to remind you you take multicolor images, here's the typical distribution. but as you enter, you start to pick up a little bit of flux and you pick up more flux. and the reason for this is of course the interplay between the allows you to pick up which have suppressed small amounts of hydrogen. and this is how we first identified hydrogen galaxies, this has been a way we have detected galaxies. after detecting these galaxies and counting them up, the first thing you do is of course create a luminosity function. rebecca is already talking about this and highlighted the problem that we've had in getting a true luminosity function of high red shift. what you see on the left is number of galaxies on the y axis and luminosity on the x axis, luminosity increasing and the deep ground-based surveys have highlighted the fact that the bright galaxies seem to be more abundant compared to the schechter luminosity function which was used to from surveys like the ultradeep field, that's true both at red shift 8 and red shift 9. in this paper they argue it's more consistent with a double parallel. but of course, the point is, single pencil beam ultradeep surveys are extremely useful since they provided the first insights into what the luminosity function might look like, we absolutely need complementary wide area observation. without those, we will not be able to get a complete picture on what the galaxy luminosity is doing at the right end and also where the agn luminosity function is compared to the storm forming galaxy luminosity function. the biggest problem we have right now is these are all color-based selections, we desperately need some very good spectroscopic confirmation. they are still faint and

challenging to do with ground-based spectroscopy. heavy contamination by late type I and t dwarfs, which is a well-known problem. are not the only contaminants, these are heavily dust obscured sources like some of the j dropouts, so we know there are compact dust obscured sources which can behave like hydrogen galaxies. and finally, hydrogen galaxies are rather compact, it's very hard to separate compact agn from star-forming galaxies. at hst resolution it gets much easier as rebecca showed some nice images of observation for some of these candidates. so that's the nice way to separate agn from star-forming galaxies and get relative contributions. but i think the overarching point here is we desperately need more spectroscopy for confirmation. and once we have that, we'd like to see if the galaxy luminosity function of any red shift matches the dark matter halo red shift, at the bright end here as i mentioned earlier the difference between the galaxy luminosity function and the dark matter halo mass function is supposed to be a tracer of agn feedback, and the same thing here, the difference is supposed to be interstellar feedback. so that's the idea anyway, we'd like to actually measure it and see which epoque is the difference between the two. moving along, as i said there is a need for multi-wavelength, without the information we would not get a complete picture of galaxy evolution. in this case, this happened a few years ago where we used a very deep spitzer imaging to characterize some of these hydrogen galaxies. so y axis is -- x axis is wavelength. the points are a combination of hubble, and spitzer photography. and the spectroscopic red shift was from in this case. what we found is, we took a while to identify this, certain bands of the spitzer bands always have an excess about the underlying best fit model, that's shown by the red arrow. the residuals from the best fit are shown in the lower panel, and i'll use the pointer here, so you guys can see things better. okay, i hope that helps. you can see this clear excess in a single band, which there is a dual shown here. this is a systematic, not just one galaxy. we find that 70% of galaxies around red shift 5 seem have this excess in the spitzer bands. it took us a while to figure it out but it appears that is because of nebular h alpha mission. we are seeing excess and broadband, which moves are the equivalent of the line omission. and what does the equivalent of the line a mission? 2,000 in the most extreme cases, if you hundred and less extreme cases. yes that is a selection effect, it would not be down here because low equal input emission would not correspond to an excess. but what is surprising is we find 70% of galaxies which are in this red shift band have equal inputs, which are a few hundred to 1,000. and several times greater than the equilibrium out red shift 2 and narrowband imaging. if you would look at samples you would say that's extreme the surprising and extreme the unlikely, but fortunately after these results came out at lower redshifts were refined and spectroscopy services, and some galaxies -- which is a very small fraction of galaxies -- is up there over a few hundred to 2,000. after he found them at all these intermediate redshifts even found them and sloan, a very small fraction of galaxies which have such high equilibrium. this is actually a case where the hydrogen galaxies allowed us to get a better understanding of how the extreme sources in the lower redshifts universe. so let's try to understand why and where this extreme with nebular emission comes from. as the name suggests, it's due to ionized gas and it's due to gas which is ionized by the radiation field of massive stars. as you can see in this block which shows luminosity as a function of wavelength, the solid lines are the total emission, while the dashed line shows you the nebular emission and the dotted line shows you nebular line thus continuing emission. so what you see here is in black and you have a typical imf. minus 2.3, and then read you have a top-heavy imf where dnd m goes minus 1.4. there's a lot of formats of stars, rather unsurprisingly you have that because luminosity of stars goes 2.5, you are putting a lot more ionizing photons, the temperatures is also hotter so you are getting more protons. ionizes the gas, and you get more continuum emission as well as more lime emission which is why for a top-heavy ims, you get more line emissions and a stronger emission compared to imf. there is another phenomenon, as you know massive stars die out quickly. live fast, die young. and so at the nebular to stellar emission ratio on the y axis as a function of time, the regular emission dies out very, very quickly and you have a burst. on a timescale which is corresponding to the age of the most massive stars. however if you have continuous star formation, what happens is yes, you have this peak in the nebular emission ratios when the first massive stars turn on but as the star formation continues, you are putting out more and more ionizing flux and the stellar mass tends to increase so the nebular to stellar emission ratio doesn't completely drop off, it is going for longer periods of time. so those are models, let's look at data on it on the right panel. and that's the squares show you the location of every single hydrogen galaxy which we've been able to characterize as multi-wavelength imaging. what you see is not everything to the left of this block, because that would indicate the star formation. there is a population of sources out here which are a way to right of this block, and this block it would be way over here. how do you explain this? and the paper goes into this in great detail, the most likely scenario here is these are all burst star formations, hierarchal merging of the things out here are due to gradual accretion of gas onto the stars. and the distribution of this population seems to be 50/50, both based on logical information as well as based on physical characterization such as this. and so, nebular emission is a very sensitive tracer of star formation and by compiling the strength of the nebular emission with the age of stellar population we can identify how the galaxies are being

powered. moving right along, there is something unusual about this, as i alluded to here. we are distributing, if you look at the strengths of these lines they are way above, so in this block it's in the top right here. why is it so strong? it's not purely because of age, in certain cases it seems to me because you need to have something else apart from a young stellar population, and that's shown in this model here of the h alpha. if you have a low stellar population your values will be down here, 0.01, 0.02 depending on age. the only way you can get stellar population which has a strong nebular to stellar emission ratio is by changing the imf slope and changing the metallicity. you can change it even more by putting a certain amount of angular momentum into the stars. how does angular momentum help? when stars rotate, there's more convective mixing. when you have more convective mixing, you have more hydrogen burning so that increases the temperature and luminosity, it increases the luminosity and because it increases temperature, it increases the nebular to stellar emission ratio. so yes, changing the imf results in a higher nebular to emission ratio, also can get the same effect by having angular momentum in these stars which improves convective mixing. again, this is the model so you put the galaxies on it, your galaxies would be down here at around 0.01. that is consistent with having a imf, he would not need to have it to explain these. as you go to higher and higher red shift, the median of the sample is up here at 0.1. which is an order of magnitude higher. so what that means is the factor of 10 more ionizing photon flux coming out with red shift compared to stars in the local universe. is this because of a top-heavy imf, is it due to increased binary fraction? or is this due to stars with angular momentum? that's a big question. andreea: 5 minutes. ranga: thanks. so just to wrap up that topic, the only way we can is by looking at x-ray binary population, and there's starting to be some great work using the deep field, about six microseconds. increasing with red shift, and this paper argues that it's maybe because of a change in stellar population. moving on, there has been a lost decade, it is no doubt. we have had significant challenges in characterizing the hydrogen population and so until jwst launches we aren't able to get a handle on what middle line and continuum ratios are doing. also, there has been significant confusion in spitzer data which makes follow-up of a large sample of hydrogen galaxy challenging. and so we need the superior resolution to be able to get robust properties and nebular line emission. moving right along, dust content we have heard a number of talks about. there are large, large uncertainties in the hydrogen universe. the best technique we have is the slope to characterize the evolving dust content of galaxies, and should in principle form within 10 million years of star formation. but it does not seem to be very much evidence of dust, we do not know if this is a selection effect because you wouldn't be able to detect it in uv, or is this actually something that we don't understand? just to summarize this, the uncertainty in how much dust obscured star formation there is at red shift 3 and 4 is very, very large, possibly an order of magnitude. and we need to get a better handle on that through spectroscopy of hydrogen galaxies as well as wider surveys with elma. alma doesn't find as many hydrogen galaxies as one would imagine, that means the large grains which are contributing to millimeter emissions. finally, no talk on hydrogen galaxy evolution problems would be complete without re-ionization, and its between properties and grb rates. this article in these four panels i tried to summarize the state of affairs. as you can see they have large uncertainties, the lines are two types of parameter, the star formation rate density is a function of red shift and you can see that if you take the uv luminosity function as it is at red shift 3 and 4 it is slightly below what the grb rates is. we need to have shallower drop-off in the star formation rate density of high red shift which may be due to cosmic variance, it's a tiny field so we don't really detect all the galaxies. so we need to have a more complete sample of both the hydrogen galaxy population as well as grb rates. if you do the census, take the higher star formation rate into account, with a top-heavy imf, you find that the re-ionization is trivial. goes from 0 to unity by red shift 6, we are able to match the long-duration grb rates, able to measure the stellar mass density, also able to account for the optical depth to the photons. none of this requires isk fractions, you can do this with fractions of 10% and clumping factors for the, this has the added benefit that it's a possible route to black holes. i think the top-heavy imf is a panacea and i think spectroscopy will shed more light on this. so to conclude, balancing the re-ionization photon budget is trivial, even with low escape fractions. the ionizing photon flux traced using nebular emission is a factor of ten stronger than at low z. is essential to distinguish whether x-ray binaries are driving some of this or whether this turbulence in the ism responsible. roman will be crucial for identifying galaxies and probing galaxy properties as a function of large-scale structures, this requires a k short filter which is a long word of the longest filter used right now and spectroscopic followed up with jwst. i shall end with the slide, if we really want headlines in 2028 roma discovers a galaxy 250 after the big bang, and it's dusty. we need something like they k sharp filter which will find something such as 15 and 17 and ages of 250 million years. thanks very much. andreea: many thanks, ranga. we have a question, and i encourage you to go back to the slack channel after this. this question is from janet, instead of a top-heavy imf, how about a possibility of a higher mass image? the so-called very high mass stars more massive than 100 are not typically accounted for and populations, but. ranga: we have looked at changing the high mass up to 250, 300. the models at those matters are somewhat uncertain, because the lifetime is much shorter,

ionizing photon flux from those supermassive stars is not adequate to account for both the strong nebular emission as well as the ubiquity of the strong nebular emission. so you need to -- that's why putting in a population of ultra massive stars which are 200 or 250 solar mass is not adequate to account for that. andreea: many thanks. we don't have time for additional questions, but if you could please go back to the slack, there are probably more interactions there.

So the next talk is by **Dr. Manda Banerji**, from the University of Southampton, and she will tell us about galaxy science, the need for infrared data. can you share your slides? I will give you a warning after 10 minutes.

Manda: thank you very much for allowing me to speak at this conference, i want to speak to you in my role as one of the galaxy collaboration cochairs about the incredible galaxy finds that will be enabled by combining data from the vera rubin observatory with the nancy roman telescope. so, firstly, as a female astronomer working in the field it's really an incredible privilege to be talking about these two facilities that have been named after pioneering female scientists. and as you can see from these descriptions that i've put together, they are very, very complement. rubin is a ground-based facility, has a state-of-the-art camera. a 3,200 megapixel camera with an enormous field of view. because it's ground-based, it will provide resolution of about half, and covers a wavelength. roman is of course much higher in resolution but a much smaller field of view, and it extends the wavelength coverage. and excitingly in 2020, both of these facilities will have the capability to conduct observations, although with different cadence. so let me just introduce the lsst galaxies science collaboration. lsst is the legacy survey of space-time which will be conducted with the rubin observatory over the next decade or so. and the lsst funding extends to the construction of rubin and the operation, so the result of that there are eight self managed, self govern the science teams that are preparing to do science with the lsst data. and to the lsst collaboration is one of those teams, i'm currently one of the cochairs at two of the previous cochairs are also at this conference. so we are a growing science collaboration, there's lots to be done before we have rubin's first flight. just a reminder that the u.s. and chilean institutes have data access rights, and we are currently going through a process of negotiating estate access rights for international partners to be a the project. these are the working groups that we currently are structured in and you can see these six working groups together with an overall survey strategy committee are designed to address the very broad range of questions that lsst will probe in terms of galaxy formation. and pretty much all of these science areas, the roman data will greatly enhance the science that will be possible with lsst. of course i don't have time to go into details about all of the science areas but what i will do is briefly picked some examples in the science areas that i've highlighted here in orange. and again, in the slide you can find the working group leads for each of them, some of them are at the conference but again, i encourage you if you are interested to get in touch with those individuals over with myself. so let me start with this, this has been one of the most active areas within the lsst galaxy science collaboration, just because the enormous field of view of lsst will really open up new discoveries. so here the extended wavelength coverage of roman as well as the high angular resolution will be really beneficial. when it comes to dwarf galaxies, lsst will start to become incomplete for low stellar mass and at high redshifts beyond one. the roman infrared data will really help in this regime. in terms of studies of the intracluster light fraction and the infrared you are less affected by the evolution of the stellar population compared to the optical. that allows more reliable icl fraction, particularly in the high redshifts universe compared to what's possible from the optical data alone. also very actively involved in the lsst low brightness effort. when it comes to the study of galaxy morphology, there is a beautiful synergy between me sensitivity to extended brightness that rubin offers and the high angular resolution of roman. you can see nice examples in the top panel of galaxy mergers, and a combination of the roman end rubin data will allow you to get incredibly detailed pictures of these kind of galaxy mergers into the high redshifts universe. that vastly improves statistics on studying galaxy morphology. there's also been a lot of ethics on quantifying the improvements that the roman will allow when adding that to the lsst spectrometry. these show you that particularly at high redshifts, the addition of near infrared data allows you to not only reduce scatter on photometric redshifts but also vastly improve the outlier fractions. if you compare in the right-hand panel the blue curve which is a fraction of outliers relative to the red which is including the near infrared roman spectrometry you can see you need the near infrared to be able to meet the lsst science requirements out to the high redshifts. of course, for galaxy science we are not just interested in getting a single red shift estimates, we also want to get a whole host of other parameters such as stellar mass, dust content. the infrared data is extremely beneficial to not only getting additional constraints, will also allow us for a lsst galaxies. the high redshifts universe, this is an area of office synergy where you really need the infrared data

combined with the optical data where these high redshifts galaxies and quasars to be able to discover them. the left-hand panel shows recent examples from our group of using dark energy survey data in combination with data to find these quasars with a red shift above 6.5. as rebecca bowler showed in her talk on the right-hand panel, we can see that the very bright high redshifts galaxies, which you can discover using ground-based surveys, you need large areas, they are very, very rare. they have very interesting morphology, multiple components emerges and so roman will allow us to study the morphologies of these bright, high redshifts galaxies that will be discovered with the rubin observatory and allow us to characterize their properties in much greater detail. and then moving to a topic that's much closer to my own interests, with this next generation of surveys we will also be able to probe an incredible detail the connection between black holes and their host galaxy, this is already possible with current generations of widefield optical and infrared surveys. i'm showing you a couple of examples here, the left panel you can see this as a quasar at a red shift of about 2.5 seen in the dark energy survey data and vista infrared survey data. what you see in the top panel is in the dark energy survey image, and when you look in the infrared you see this very bright source. what you find is that it's best fit by an obscured quasar which dominates the infrared light, shown by the magenta and a relatively unobscured star-forming host galaxy shown by blue. and then on the right-hand panel is an example of the opposite happening, this is now data from spitzer, this is an x-ray discovered originally in a survey, what you can see is the blue light is dominated by the quasar, you have this blue point source. but then when you look at the extended emissions, it's red in color so the host galaxy is actually an older host galaxy and the light in the infrared is being dominated by the old stellar populations in the host galaxy. this kind of disentangling of the agn and host galaxy will be able to do for much larger samples and in much greater details with the combination of rubin and roman. not only that, the angular resolution of roman will allow us to separate out the agn emission and host galaxy emission and to be able to do separate reads of those different components separated out. so in the last few minutes, i just want to move on from science to talk a bit about the precursor infrared surveys that we already have on hand that will give us lots of insight into the infrared side prior to roman and prior to euclid, which is also coming along very soon. and again, rebecca mentioned this in her talk, i think it's fair to say that vista telescope has been the workhorse instrument for widefield infrared surveys over the last decade or so. and in addition to -- andrea: two more minutes. manda: that's fine. so in addition to the programs i have been conducted using vista, there's also been a very large number of public surveys and these tables are just summarizing those. everything from the hemispheric surveys covering 20,000 square degrees of the southern sky to relatively shallow depth to single points such as altavista going much, much deeper over a smaller area of size. and the ones that i've highlighted in orange are the extragalactic surveys which are most relevant to the conference. and i particularly want to advertise the survey i'm leading, where we are building up deep infrared coverage in the lsst scenes, and three of the four drilling fields altavista. this is building on observations that have already been conducted as part of the video survey, we are doing the observations in a cadence manner, so taking them every 8-20 days which really is first opportunity to look at the near infrared. so this is just showing you the sky coverage of those vista surveys, everything from all hemisphere surveys to the very deep field. most of this data now is publicly available. so one of the things we are leading within the u.k., this is one of our in-kind contributions to the lsst project. it is to develop a joint pixel processing pipeline to be able to get spectrometry at the same time from the lsst and vista imaging. and all of the hard work is being done by rafael shirley, at the university of southampton and he's been using images as a proxy for lsst. and multiplying the rubin subset to be able to jointly process the pixels from vista telescope. so what this infrastructure will do is provide a modification of the rubin stack to be able to deal with pixels from other telescopes. while our current focus is on data with similar resolution as lsst, we are also interested in extending the efforts to cope with data of different angular resolutions. and the other thing we are going to do is provide the infrared catalogs putting together over the entire southern sky to the astronomy community. so i think i'm nearly out of time, so i'm just going to leave my summary slide and i'll put these slides up on slack with the links that give you more information about lsst galaxies. if you're interested in lsst galaxies or interested in the vista infrared surveys, please message me on slack or please find one of the other lsst galaxy attending the conference. i'll finish there. andrea: thank you, many thanks for this very informative talk. so one question before, but i will encourage you after this to go back to the slack channel. in addition to roman, how do you think with higher velocity resolution will help leverage the reach of rubin data? manda: absolutely, it's going to be absolutely essential. so, the form of widefield spectroscopic facility, there's a couple of ground based ones that are coming online. the one that i know most about and most heavily involved in, which is going on the vista telescope in 2022. a lot of the targets for that will be from rubin. so, that's going to be absolutely have to go in tandem with the multi-wavelength data to be able to do the galaxy science with rubin. andrea: thank you. and so, we will move on to the next talk.

Next talk is by **Lucia Pozzetti** from inf Bologna. She will talk to us about galaxy formation and evolution in the era of euclid. Would you please share the slides?

Lucia: In this talk, I will do the galaxy evolution in the era of euclid, and let me summarize some of the characteristics of the euclid satellite mission. substituted by 1.2-meter telescope, which will be launched in 2022. so the launch is approaching, and the mission duration will be over six years. the instruments on board are an optical camera and near infrared camera, with a field-of-view of half a degree. the euclid consortium made by 16 countries with more than 2,000 members of which more than 1,000 are active. so the main mission of euclid is cosmological, to investigate natural matter and using -- and also galaxy clusters. what this means is cosmology would be a huge gain. using very large samples and very large volume, will allow us to study with higher distribution functions with also, while a high quality imaging will allow unique morphological studies, mergers, and weak lensing will allow -- and finally will allow to study star formation in galaxies at red shift 1 and the metal content from emission lines paired so euclid will map the sky with 15,000-degree, and deep survey. both are covered. and with a very high quality imaging psf. the imaging will be quite deep. will be similar to the images from the ground, and in particular the euclid wide optical will be able to get information from more of the current survey. if we look at hst, provided up to 15 and 20 square degree of high-quality. from using euclid in just one year we can have more than 200, at the end we will have more than three orders of magnitude increase. to study more in particular. the red grism and blue grism, the survey will be covered by. and h alpha will be in the range from nine to 1.8. the survey will be covered by red and blue grism, h alpha will be covered in a larger red shift range. as you can see, the deep end will provide an order of magnitude larger than the previous spectroscopic findings. so how many star-forming galaxies we can detect? using also to provide some estimation for roman telescope, and we found it will be on an order of 2,000 square degrees, which is in agreement also with the data from infrared spectroscopy. so at the end we will have 50, and multiple lines from h alpha. so we will have also an order of a million and multiple lines of orders of ten to the fourth. so this is what we can derive for expectations, galaxy, galaxy masses, as I'll show you in the next slide. so to provide some scientific, the galaxy marks in particular. the flagship market, which has been built in collaboration in zurich, and barcelona. so with the old photometry, we were able to estimate emission rates from photometry, and we'll be able to scaling relation with galaxies similar to what has been done. and also to describe the difference between different populations of star-forming galaxies. using spectroscopy instead we can measure flux systems from h alpha and also some of the information like metallicity from single spectra, and also emission line from some fraction of the galaxy. with those data again come a weekend construct emission line diagram, which will be at least a few hundred. and relation metallicity, mass relation and here I see some expectation based on the imaging. and so with those data weaken find distribution, evolution of some galaxy and also with the euclid we can reconstruct halo mass and some halo properties to study the galaxy evolution as a function of property. but also higher red shift, agn and so on as I'll show you in the next slide. I can show you some possibility from images that will give a similar image to -- this will allow increased with spectroscopy mergers selection of a merger system, and also allows the classification on the galaxy and typical properties of such system and subject matter in the fashion of environment and mass and every thing we can reconstruct. strong lensing, instead we can in a part of the galaxy and also using weak lensing and combining lensing we can infer some information with stellar mass, depends on the imf. andreea: 2 minutes. lucia: currently only a small numbers allows this kind of study, so finally, from strong and to weak lensing we can also study the relation between stellar mass and halo mass and function of stellar mass in the local universe. and in the higher red shift universe, we can select lyman break galaxy. and to understand this in particular the bright and, a function of the lyman break galaxy and also a sample of high red shift quasar. so the last two slides, red blue grism in deep survey which allows to detect with the blue grism a population of galaxies. and here I show some spectra, and the image we can provide sizes, morphology for studies such as in this particular important population. finally, the most important case blue grism in the deep survey will be red shift 7, you can see specific assimilation. and we expect to find 2,000 meters. and even more if we can reach an deeper flux. and I'll leave you with this summary, which will give you the main sense of the euclid data center with ultradeep imaging, and h alpha emitters in particular. physical properties and halo masses from the weak lens. andreea: thank you very much for this very inspiring talk about what euclid and roman can do, and there's one question about -- so you've given us all this information about wonderful questions we will be able to answer with euclid and roman, and one question is what do you think you could end roman can or should do in terms of available data, access, et cetera to facilitate worldwide multi-wavelength collaborations and maximize the science productivity? lucia: I think with euclid it would be important for the bright end of the objects and for optical images. and the roman

data will be more supportive of the luminosity function and study of the -- i think they would be complementary and possible to use the data to constrain the whole range of luminosity and to compare optical engineer infrared images which will allow different morphology of different populations. andrea: thank you very much.

So we will move on to the next talk, which is by **Lukas Zalesky** at the Institute for Astronomy, and he will tell us about the Hawaii twenty square degree survey synergy with next-generation space space telescope. I look forward to hearing about that. I will give you a two-minute warning.

Lukas: Okay, great. all right, first let me thank you for giving me this opportunity to speak to you here at this awesome conference, we've heard all week about a number of exciting science topics for things we should look forward to for the next decade of astronomy, especially within the context of galaxy evolution. we hope to continue that theme and give us one more thing to be excited about, which is the hawaii twenty square degree survey and the synergy able provide with the next generation space telescopes. i want to start by thinking my advisor david sanders as well as the scientists i've had the opportunity to work with. they played a lot of the groundwork that has enabled my dissertation as well as john weaver graduate students at copenhagen and university of california at riverside. let's get started. i'll just start by giving you a brief overview of what the hawaii 20 survey is. then i will talk about options for synergy and upcoming missions like euclid, roman, and date of ust. within this context i will give you a brief overview and to dive deeper into the programmatic red shift capabilities we heard earlier about. and i'll end with giving a brief touch on what we should expect for hawaii two-0 data products and what will be released. the hawaii two-0 degree survey or h2o, i'll use these names interchangeably, as an ultradeep survey covering 210 square degree fields. the north ecliptic pole and euclid deep field for. spitzer made infrared imaging. it's the spitzer data that separates it from similar efforts. as you can see here, where i am showing total allocated time for these different components, we have an incredible amount of time that was awarded to us. the legacy survey which is the largest allocation of spitzer time ever granted and it matches the depth of our subaru hyper supprime-cam imaging, and it allows us to get stellar mass rather than relying on some type of uv stellar mass relationship. after 2022, we will also get deep euclid imaging, as we heard from lucia in the previous talk there are deep portions of the euclid survey, they happen to be to have these deep fields which i will talk more about in a moment. on the top right i am showing the signal limiting magnitudes and on the right i am showing the of different components. just to get a feeling for what the completed north ecliptic pole looks like, from this view we can't get a real feeling for what the source of that density is that we are dealing with. so i can zoom in a bit further. there's over 12,000 fields we detect, we will detect over 5 million sources within ten square degrees, 10 million over the full hawaii two-0 area. this depth and volume that's really angering a lot of the science that we hope to do with h2o. as we heard from micaela bagley on tuesday, it's important to sample over large regions of the sky when you are measuring the galaxy stellar mass function. you don't want to be stuck in avoid, so it's important to have cosmologically relevant volumes measuring properties like this. i'll be more exquisite about some of our goals here, one of the things we want to do is to trace the stellar mass across redshifts 3-7. ideally, with h2o data we will paint to the most precise measurements of the galaxy stellar mass to date. we also want to trace the growth of dark matter halos, because we are measuring such a large volume we can also trace the growth of dark matter halos and investigate the evolution of stellar to hail or mass relation. we also want to constrain the properties of dark energy using the nonlinear power spectrum at high redshifts. spectroscopic leak and from these and learn more about them throughout observation and learn about their escape fractions and things like that, their ionization capabilities. we want to locate and study the first galaxies to seize star formation. one of the more exciting discoveries in the past ten years is there seems to be a population of galaxies already in place at red shift to three when the universe is already 3 billion years old. how did they get so massive so quickly? what led them to cease their star formation? with hawaii two-0 we hope to find a statistically significant number of these galaxies. so why am i talking about this at the room in 2020 conference? what do we need the near infrared photometry for? there are a number of specific information encoded within the near galaxy, what i would like to focus on is the redshifts created in the universe. the roman opens up the universe for investigation, and on the right here i'm showing a galaxy of roughly seven or so. it's not detected in any of the bands blue, and it's detected in channel 1 at channel to drown. with the high-quality spectrometry i have i'm able to say this galaxy is likely to be at redshifts 7. as soon as this galaxy drops out of the band, i was only detecting channel 1 and 2 and redshifts 7.4. suddenly i'm left with a single galaxy color such as channel one minus drown to and nothing but a upper limits. the weak and really not say anything of interest at all about this galaxy, all we can say is that it's likely to be at high redshifts but as far as properties go we are at a loss. fortunately, h2o will get

euclid data, some of the deepest because as i said before the h2o survey deals are the primary calibration fields for the euclid mission targeted by the deep survey. it goes to magnitudes deeper than the wide survey, also benefits from blue and red to grism spectroscopy so they will have some of the best and most representative examples. another comparison i'd like to touch on is the accommodation of lsst and roman. we heard two talk prior about all the different reasons you should be excited about that. it's true, the combination of romans high latitude survey and rubens lsst will provide one of the best data sets for extragalactic signs we've ever had. the most enormous cosmic volume we've ever had and we will really nail down with sufficient statistics a lot of the properties we are interested in. the problem is a lot of the high redshifts science that many of us are interested and will have to wait at least ten years for the completion of lsst and for it to reach its final tenure depth. foot the back fortunately, hawaii two-0 will enable this science years in advance while also providing a view of lsst and roman and miniature. we obtained near equal depth as you can see where i'm showing the signal limiting magnitudes while still probing cosmologically significant volume. within 20 square degrees we expect to find numerous clusters and numerous voids. these will be important for developing the tools we need to really probe cosmology to high redshifts. lastly, i'd like to just leave with food for thought, whether or not roman should target nep or eff. we heard from anton, so here i'm just getting some of the selling points beyond the fact that they are both legibly low galactic intensity. the continuous viewing zone, eff is not quite within the viewing zone. we can talk more about these off-line. i'd like to talk about photometric redshifts. all of the extragalactic science with h2o or lsst and euclid and roman are contingent upon high-quality photometric redshifts. how well can we determine the red shift of these galaxies? so to answer this question, i'd like to perform a realistic test. by realistic, i mean not dependent upon a mock catalog where i know the true galaxy just region but instead a realistic data set with real data. here i'm using the cosmos 2020 catalog prepared by john weaver. and i investigate three key scenarios. i have only the hsc band, in the second i have all of the h2o bands and in the third i have h2o plus euclid or roman. i don't have the time to dive into detail about my method, if you're interested in what i did please let me know on slack. the punch line is that temper fitting, i'm not doing any complicated. there's been a lot of work within this area, so i point to these recent publications where people have done similar work if you want to get more detail on this. let's jump right in and look at hsc. the spectroscopic totals 14,085, they range from 0 to 26.5. i've done no cleaning to the sample aside from ensuring they have the easy bands of 1.5 to ensure the galaxies wouldn't have been detected if they work in the h2o survey. you can see immediately from the scatter and outlier fraction this is not a pretty picture. this is not so good, especially at high red shift, we are getting almost everything wrong. i point here was not necessarily to build the best possible five band photometric redshifts, i'm sure other have done better. all they wanted to do was apply the same method systematically to the same data set and just change the input filter to see how well we could constrain it. moving ahead to h2o, we can already see a dramatic improvement. i want to just flip back and forth so you can see how dramatic the improvement is. the improvement extends out from low wed shift to high redshifts, the scatter is less than .03, the outlier is less than 10%. this means that we can already do a lot with the data sets. the science capabilities improve further if we include the near infrared. as you can see when i go to the next slide, i'll flip back and forth so you can pay attention to the residuals to see how much they change when i include the near infrared filters. the scatter change goes down .02, almost a 20% increase or improvement rather. on the next slide, i just summarize these results with three different scenarios. the punch line obviously here is that the near infrared combination provides the best photometric redshifts possible. .02 is the scatter that was needed to perform a lot of lsst science, we are really meeting what needs to be done with this filter set. i also want to emphasize that although there's not a quite huge improvement as one might expect from including the near infrared filters, my spectroscopic sample is limited to redshifts less than 6.5. what motivated my discussion about the near infrared filters was that it would be extremely important at redshifts greater than 6.5. these galaxies are not represented within my sample. so lastly i can tell you about the hawaii two-0 data products. currently we have a skyview were in place, if you want to look at color or black-and-white images you can follow this link and assume around the completed areas of the survey, created by our postdoc department. we also have three publications in preparation, a survey overview a methodology paper and a machine learning techniques paper to predict galaxy colors. we also hope to release our first catalog by the end of 2022, which should contain over 10 million galaxies over 20 square degrees. we also hope to make our image mosaics publicly available by 2023 as well. so let me just conclude with my summary, hawaii two-0 is an ultradeep survey covering the north ecliptic pole and these bands. there's numerous opportunities for synergy like jwst and roman, jwst is already planning one of its deep drilling fields in the north ecliptic pole. and i described some of the hawaii two-0 data products from the sky view or, future publications, catalogs, and images. with that, i am happy to take any questions. andreea: thank you lukas, you do have a number of questions so i encourage you to go to the slack. so just to be sure, the spectroscopic data will become public in 2023? lukas: our

spectroscopic for the north ecliptic pole i believe that's the case, we hope to make all of these data public. once they are collected in the science is completed. ideally what we want is to be done before the launch of euclid.

Andreea: wonderful, thank you. and then what are the approximate limits for h2o around 7?

Lukas: okay, so we should get down to at least ten to the ten solar masses or so, devious analysis have shown that our mass complete limit is actually pretty similar to cosmos 2015. it's really limited by the depth of the spitzer data, so the spitzer data is really the limiting stellar mass we can focus on. so i spitzer data is similar to 2015, so i suggest you look at the work from 2017 to see what their stellar mass limit is, it's pretty similar to that. andreea: fantastic, thank you very much. we'll move on, please go back to slack if you can for additional questions.

And the next talk up will be by Adam, about resolving problems in galaxy formation with HST and girmos. Adam, i will interrupt you at 10 minutes to give you a two-minute warning.

Adam: you guys can see my slides? Maybe i'll just quickly switch to the other computer.

Andreea: should we move on to the invited talk or give Adam 1 minute? So I will take this opportunity to encourage again people to add questions in the slack and for speakers to please interact with everyone on the slack and respond to questions.

Adam: Sorry about that guys, i am on a different laptop than yesterday. okay, so very happy to be here and talk to you about resolving issues in galaxy formation. this talk is going to be about getting resolved images of galaxies and trying to learn about galaxies that way. and this picture shows you the scale of the problem, a nice nearby galaxy where we get tons of beautiful information and here's an analog of m106, with ground-based data and you see the lack of information at high redshifts. so i want to quickly put my work in context, and say that we've been working hard over the last 15 years in galaxy observation work and a lot of the people at this conference are people doing this, trying to take the census of all the galaxies that are out there. how many galaxies are there as a function of redshifts, as a function of mass? how much star formation can we see? i want to give us a pat on the back because i think we've actually done this pretty darn well cared we've seen this before, we mapped out when the star formation occurs in the universe over much of cosmic time, mapped out where the stellar mass is and it's a beautiful plot, but there's still some major outstanding problems. the things that are really bothering me and keeping me up at night is now we know when the stars form, but we don't know how galaxies actually grow. is it at high redshifts through star formation, is it a merger of smaller galaxies? is there this inside out growth or in growth? and why do galaxies have morphologies they do? we have clues on this and we've done work on this, but a lot of these questions are still outstanding. and of course the one that really keeps us up at night which is why does this curve turnover? why does the star formation density go up and come back down? and we've appealed to agn, although it's still a very difficult thing to observe. i like to think provocative statements, i know we are going to measure all of these things too much greater accuracy with the nancy roman telescope, but i would argue that if you put infinitely small aero bars, it's not clear to me that it really answers the question that i just post. it's useful, and we will do it and i think it will be helpful for various things, but i don't like it really solves galaxy formation. and so i want to propose to you is that the next 15 years what we should be doing is actually resolving high redshifts galaxies. and now that we know when galaxies form, we actually want to know where they grow, when do bulges appear...

Andreea: We can no longer hear you. Did we lose them? I don't think he can hear us or we cannot hear him. He's still at the same slide, so it seems like something is stuck. okay, well i think his computer is crashed or died. I think we should move on to Brant. Are you ready?

Andreea: Hi, Brant. We have the pleasure to hear the invited talk now, and go back to Adam if possible at the end. So **Brant Robertson** from University of California Santa Cruz, I will interrupt you at 20 minutes for a warning, apart from that we look forward to hearing your talk.

Brant: Thanks a lot, My name is Brant Robertson, i'm the p.i. of the roman extragalactic potential observations team, the EXPO team, and i'm here today to talk about galaxy formation and evolution with the roman space telescope. People have been talking about science with roman this entire week and it's been great to see, this is a high level talk and i'm mostly a cheerleader for all of the work that everyone here is doing. my role as the p.i. of expo and as a member of the formulation science working group for roman, but i will get into the details of some specific investigations that we've been doing as expo in addition to the broader scope of what roman can do for extragalactic science. hopefully as you are providing questions in the slack, feel free to ask me broadbrush questions or even more detailed questions about the capabilities of roman, i'll try to get back to you as best i can. so think you for this opportunity to talk. so i'll start with the broad overview of observable history of the universe, you may have seen this before. of course early on, the universe was very hot and dense but eventually expanded and cooled to the point where protons and electrons could re-combine to neutral hydrogen. the universe released the radiation, the cosmic microwave background we see today. afterward the universe, most of the gas was neutral and this is before a large-scale structure grew in abundance but eventually as the universe continued to grow through its own self gravity the first stars and galaxies could begin to form at the center. as those first stars and galaxies produced ionizing radiation, they could form bubbles of ionized gas around them. as they grew in size and abundance, eventually the bubbles started overwriting the galaxy population and once that happened through path of ionizing hydrogen particles and most of the universe was quickly ionizing and about the first billion years of cosmic history. we call this re-ionization. after re-ionization, of course we all know that modern galaxies form in abundance, especially red shift 2 as the universe begins to expand faster through the influence of dark energy and led to the galaxy population that we enjoy now. and so, the nancy grace roman space telescope will be one of the essential facilities for studying galaxy formation and evolution, we are really going to be enjoying a new golden age of study, it will be fantastic with roman, jwst, with rubin that i most interested in. you may know i'm on the committee for the survey with jwst, i'm very interested in james webb as well i will talk about the synergy there. this conference is about roman and i'm really excited about roman, there's so much we can do with nancy grace roman space telescope over an extremely wide range of red shift. i'll give an overview of that science and then talk some more about particulars you might be interested in. so i wanted to introduce the extragalactic attentional observations committee, there's a variety of science investigation teams for roman. expo is the team that is designed to investigate and to develop and advocate for the extragalactic science with roman space telescope. and a lot of our members are here, these are the original investigators of the program, i know mark dickinson, harry ferguson and jenny green, our postdocs and students. know are here as well, so. as you can see, we are really part of the community. we are not all the same stuff, we are at institutions like space telescope or academic institutions, and really advocates and interested in what roman will do. we thought a lot about it, we are pushing for that science and all of your talks are really invigorating for us. so if you have any questions about what roman is going to do for extragalactic science, please reach out. so this is the diagram, this is the star formation rate density as a function of time in the universe, and you can see the star formation rate peak at red shift 2 and declines at higher red shift. we've been able to measure the star formation rate out to about red shift 8 or so. you might wonder how does this map to the science case for nancy grace roman? and i think that really splits into four major red shift sections. at low red shift, we will be interested in the evolution of individual galaxies, galaxy morphology, and galaxy environments so we can measure the environment from some of the weak lensing surveys that roman will be able to do. and we will be able to measure at some redshifts spectroscopic red shift with grism and connect the properties of galaxies directly to their environments. at higher redshifts, of course, we can still measure the clustering in a new way for galaxies photometric, we will also be able to measure the large-scale survey and high latitude survey which is a server that would be done with nancy grace roman space telescope to measure parameters. it will also be extremely useful as a resource for all of us to do extragalactic science with roman, so that will be extremely interesting. we'll also get some handle on the relative contribution of nitrogen and h alpha. that will be measured mostly through grism, that will give us -- at higher redshifts will be able to select out agn and quasars high redshifts, a huge area to deal with so we will be able to select quasars and hopefully find some quasars at high redshifts that we can follow up from the ground or space with jwst. pushing that further back into the re-ionization, the high-resolution infrared space telescope will be able to probe for that. so that's kind of the broad topical questions, there are more detailed science questions, understanding the galaxy property and agn and quasars, gravitational lenses so with this high-resolution imaging we will be able to do with nancy grace roman and how the ir capability we can detect background sources will be able to probe the properties of dark matter in gravitation lensing clusters, that's a really important science case for galaxy evolution. we will also be able to characterize the importance of galaxies and quasars separately for re-ionization using large areas of the sky.

and since we'll be probing very deep areas of the sky as well over time, we can look at early stellar populations, potentially high redshift supernovas. those are some questions that our team has thought about. of course, you may have sought talks about the connection between dark matter halos, galaxies and here i'm just illustrating that. on the left side is a dark matter simulation that identified galaxies and halos within that dark matter situation. and what their ages were based on some analytical models. this is illustrative of how we might be able to connect galaxies and map the properties of galaxies onto the properties of dark matter halos using nancy grace roman which will have sensitivity to what the masses of halos are through weak lensing, sensitivity to the properties of the galaxies through photometry and a grism. that's a really powerful capability that roman will have that we would love for everyone here to exploit. this is the hubble ultra deep field, i was a member of the udf 12 project as a postdoc at caltech, the deep observations with hst that build on the hdf shallow observations that were taken in the ers program. these are significantly deeper observations with hst probing even further back and giving the first robust galaxies above red shift 8.5. of course, this is a small field in the sky, it's less than five square units and yet with nancy grace roman, we will be able to extend this by a factor of 100 and a single pointing with roman. i do so everything we've learned from udf, which i think has been a lot, is structured with a variety of other surveys like candels and frontier fields, we will be able to do that on a much bigger scale with much better statistics with roman. so i'm going to talk about the notional surveys with roman, of course there is the mission survey that will do cosmology, that's not fully concrete yet but it's a notional survey that would be about 2,000 square degrees with multiple bands to about 27 magnitudes. and have supporting grism spectrometry. will also be able to survey a ten to 20-degree survey, combined with may be geo-observations would help here. we know there's going to be supernova cosmology surveys, which will also be very useful as the medium area with roman in the infrared, that will be fantastic. and then of course there will be ultradeep surveys i'm sure, whether in go, this might be a single pointing of 29.5 to 38 magnitudes. you can have supporting grism. and just the box is kind illustrate differences in factors of two areas, factors of 100 and factors of two flux. so thinking about how you might do this, one of the things we've done with our team is tried to design realistically what roman surveys would look like, and so we've included overheads and exposure time and this is how -- people would ask me, how would you color a single deep imaging survey with rubin from the grounds with roman from the sky? the best way to do that is piled together these individual findings into this tile, you'd be able to use for cosmology surveys, those things worked to cover smaller fields with rubin. and so we can actually count late how long these survey stakes, what the science returns. and similarly you can look at individual pointing's as well where you take a single pointing and tile it to get a deep tile. you can see what kind of patterns provide the best imaging quality or depth with roman. that's something that we are ready have the capability of doing. and then we can see what kinds of science we will get. we will start at relatively low red shift, roman can really revolutionize galaxy surveys at red shift 1-2, we know the cosmology survey will go a long way in doing this. grism will be able to use techniques that have been used through the ages by like erica nelson, we will be able to actually reconstruct the h alpha emission profiles. if you look at the hst surveys, there are tens of thousands of galaxies with this kind of data but only if you percent have sufficient fluxes to measure both morphology and the resulting h alpha emission. this allows you to measure the star formation rate versus stellar mass properties directly, however there is relatively few of them and roman will increase these numbers. we will be able to look at this more robustly. in pursuit of this, one of the things we can do from the ground today is to understand what the roaming data will actually give us. to do that, we have to look at the properties of galaxies we will look at with grism. the best sample to build from is the mosdef sources. we are doing preparatory work where we are actually following up mosdef galaxies to try to get a sample of better exposed deeper observations to look at. and i can show you some of the state already, this program has an ongoing supported by nasa and in 2020a and 2020b, we've been able to exposed four hours of sub galaxies. you can see the top panel of the original mosdef spectrum, you can see silicon, but in the bottom panel you can see that we actually detect those lines in addition to h alpha. so we'll have about 150 objects where we've gone down to the flux limit of roman and beyond time and we can measure h alpha and galaxies down to the flux point of roman and predict how and to might contaminate h alpha. but we need to understand how they play off of one another. both for calibrating the spectroscopic survey but also understanding them. so now, i'm in talk about high red shift. this is red shift zero, many of us have seen this animation before but one many of us haven't seen what it looks like at higher red shift. if i show you the red shift 7, it looks dramatically different, much more of the massive spread out and so the number of halos of course is very much suppressed. and so our expectations about how this information will be different at higher red shift and at lower red shift. that's something that nancy grace could tell us a lot about. and expo has been very active in this, of a group has been looking at very high red shift galaxy populations and are trying to see as a function of survey how many of these galaxies will actually be able to observe and what we will be able to learn from them. so we'll have 1,000 galaxies at red shift of 10 like an ultradeep survey, we'll be able to get very many more in broader

areas. so it should be extremely exciting for looking at galaxies throughout, that's pretty fantastic. so we are looking forward to that. of course, one of the big uncertainties with high red shift galaxy populations and cosmic variance, this is a dark matter density field. once you start imaging areas like what hst can do or what candels has done, we are still pretty uncertain what the cosmic variance is, it could be above 30%, about 20% for candels. with a single roman area we will be able to get down to 12%, we should be able to do very well. adam trapp had a paper recently where he's now come up with a cosmic variance which will be useful for planning these kinds of surveys. another interesting thing about having wide area surveys, you can actually see galaxies distributed on the scale of re-ionization. showing the distribution calculated about the size of individual re-ionization bubbles during the reorganization process at red shift 7 and be able to capture the sizes of individual bubbles in individual roman points which will be great, we'll be able to understand the variations in the galaxy population, whether that's connected to reorganization or not. one of the last things i want to talk about was a deep learning framework for pixel level analysis of images with space-based data like roman. and people have been talking about deep learning but one of the things we've been able to do is say what would you actually want to get out of the deep learning? would you want to classify a picture or would you like it to classify every pixel in the image and tell you first of all whether or not there was any object of interest in that pixel to detect objects, but also once you've detected an object, what kind of object is that? that pixel that you are looking at, what kind of object is that pixel? so what ryan house and has done to work with roman is to look at a deep learning framework. and so what we do is we see the actual images from hst in this model, we scan through and classify pixel by pixel whether or not that pixel belongs to the sky, but also classifies if there is a source there, what kind of source is it? is it a regular galaxy versus star? you can see in the diagram the morphologies building up with time as we scan through, and eventually this will scan through and tell you by pixel what the morphological classification of the pixels belong to. i'll wrap up here in a moment. andreea: 4 minutes. brant: no worries, we will end a little bit sooner. so, you might say what good is using this image analysis, this deep learning framework analysis on small images of the sky? what can you possibly get out of that? well, we've already gone through and classified all of candels, we've been able to recover the 3d hst catalogs, we know our completeness levels using these learning frameworks for doing galaxies, it's all in brian's paper and every single pixel in candels has been classified. we all know for every galaxy in candels, whether those pixels belong to disk galaxy, stars, or the sky. and so we already know we can apply this already using today's supercomputers. and the deep learning framework that ryan has developed. we can already classify the entire expected roman data set, we are already there. what we are hoping to do is improve these analyses, and how sophisticated they are, how well we can use them to do photometry, measure galaxy structure, and there's been other work on individual galaxies classification in the past, here we are classifying whole images and whole service of the sky at once. so this should be a powerful technique going forward. i wanted to say just a few words about other applications, this conference has been wonderful and all of the great talks. there are some more details, there's astro 2020 science white paper that we submitted called understanding galaxy formation via near infrared surveys in the 2020s, that's especially about the roman space telescope and its capabilities. the snowmass project is ongoing, and one of the things that roman will be able to do is constrain some of the properties of dark matter by looking at gravitational lenses and quasars and gravitational lensing structure of galaxy clusters and so that something that hopefully people are tuned into with the snowmass process, and will be fundamental physics in addition to astrophysical applications that we are all very excited about. please have a look at these, i'm happy to answer any questions about those and i'd love to hear your questions. andreea: many thanks, brant. you have several questions, so please go back to slack. i will combine two questions was asked about the synergies in near infrared and in radio with observations. brant: this is something tremendously exciting and it's something that roman really represents, some of our best opportunity to connect together 21 centimeters data with observations of high red shift galaxies. with the 21 centimeters data we are able to do at least correlation functions when hopefully maps of neutral gas and in its absence, ionized gas at high red shift. if we can measure and map 21 centimeters the galaxy population at the same red shift, we will be able to finally answer this question about the ionizing fraction and re-ionization we will be able to say this bubble belongs to this galaxy or collection of galaxies and be able to convert the ub luminosity's of those galaxies into an ionizing budget that would give us the bubble. so that has a huge amount of promise may requires fairly large areas. the 21-centimeter surveys are fairly low resolution, you have to be able to serve a fairly large areas of the sky and infrared and the roman space telescope will allow us to do that. that's hugely exciting and something that roman really should be able to do, it will be able to follow-up for some galaxies lime and alpha emissions, so we'll be able to connect that as well in conjunction with the 21-centimeter and uv photometry of the galaxies. it will be interesting to map out a cluster of galaxies and how that connect with the clustering of galaxies seen with photometry that will be able to measure star formation rates and to cross correlations. i think that will be extremely exciting, there's so much going on. i'm sorry i didn't put it on the slide of different observational capabilities, that's an extremely

exciting facility and i'm sure would love to tell you more about that. andreea: now you have a question that you mentioned that the mosdef is significantly less, in your estimate of spatially resolved spectroscopic observations this will matter a lot in other sources of nonstellar ionization. brant: this is exactly the kinds of questions we are interested in looking at with mosfire, we can look at what the effects of grism are. we aren't going to be able to measure well individual lines with the grism, so things like the bbt diagram we may not be able to see directly with roman because like n2 and h alpha will be blended together. will be able to hopefully see some of that in the mosfire data and model that in the grism. and will be able to use other models for predicting with the spatial distribution of line emissions roman would see in the grism observation. this is exciting. there are already people associated with roman who are modeling the grism observations trying to predict what the grism data will look like. we hope to be able to collaborate with them in the future using the mock catalog that we've done along with observations from mosfire, trying to figure out what the grism data will look like. we are excited.

Andreea: Wonderful. Many thanks and you do have quite a few more questions so go to slack.

Now, if we could try **Adam Muzzin** again. Adam, third times a charm?

Adam: I apologize for the technical difficulties, I should blame it on Mac Catalina but i'll take the blame myself. Just to jump back where i was, i'll make the argument that we should now be spatially resolved in galaxies and brant was talking about this a moment ago as well. to kind of figure out how galaxies are growing and where they are growing over cosmic time. so what we really want to do is take these galaxies of properties we've made over cosmic time, things like stellar mass and star formation rate and map them into dimensions. so if we want to do this we need a few things, if we want to map where the stellar mass and galaxies are we need two things. we need high angular resolution data and we need multi-wavelength data so we can fit spectral imagery distributions. right now, hubble is really the only game in town. the amount of data surprisingly, because hubble has been around for a long time, it's still rather sparse. you have reasonable areas surveyed with multiple filters. nancy roman grace has enormous potential impact here and talked about some of the stuff that can be done with that. in terms of star formation, you want the same thing. you need high angular resolution but spectra will be really useful. things like mapping h alpha and other emission lines and this is where i think nancy grace roman will be really transformational, but i'm going to try to make a pitch quickly at the end that an adaptive optics in the infrared from the ground is actually going to play a really big role going forward. so let's talk about stellar mass very quickly. this is some work we are doing at york and working with the hubble frontier fields. this is a wonderful place to map out the stellar mass, you have exquisite resolution hubble data in multiple filters and you can see yet there, you can really map galaxies really well. this is work being done by a phd student working with me, vivian tan, she's mapping the stellar mass in cluster galaxies, so these are the more nearby galaxies in frontier fields. kind of skipping to the punch line you start with a galaxy like this and basically you break up every single pixel and you can fit stellar population models to it and you can go backwards and you can turn that into a map of stellar mass. once you've mapped the stellar mass this way, you can start to fit these things to parametric models and just showing matt here, the bottom right is a model fit to the stellar mass profile, and to the top right is a fit to the f160 alone, which is near infrared light. they seem similar but in fact, galaxy is more concentrated in stellar mass than it is in near infrared light. so if we really want to be getting down to where is the mass and galaxies forming, we should be mapping here in stellar mass and not just single infrared filters. so vivian has a paper coming out very shortly but what she was looking at is the structural properties of these cluster galaxies, and what you see on the top is the effective radius of galaxies versus their mass. so this is kind of the classic mass and size, and in the bottom is the same galaxies as a function of mass. one of the things we are taking is when you get down to very low mass which you can do in the frontier field, star-forming galaxies have very similar structure, they are both small and both very disklake whereas high masses are quite different. this tells you that our interpretation of this is that environment is quenching low mass star-forming galaxies relatively recently but maintaining their overall morphology whereas high mass galaxies and clusters must have quenched at a much different time, probably much earlier to a very different process because they don't look like star-forming galaxies of the same mass in the local universe. so this seems promising, but how can we do better? the problem we are facing is we really need more area. the best data sets we have to do this with our things like goods and the hubble frontier fields, there's a lot of people who have done work on this but a lot of work has been done with goods. really it's only a couple hundred square arc minutes where we can do this, we want millions of galaxies. the other thing we want is we

want more filters, the best data sets that have hubble imaging have something like seven filters in goods and up to 14 and frontier fields, that's pretty good for fitting but we love to have even more. what if you asked me what my perfect survey is, hubble-like imaging over multiple square degrees, having something like greater than 20,000 galaxies and imaging and more than 20 filters. and it turns out my perfect survey exists, it's called cosmos. cosmos has a couple square degrees and cosmos imaging and more than 30 filters. the only problem is that cosmos is ground-based imaging, not space-based we don't have the angular resolution. just to compare for you, here's the 106 image i showed you, it's really in a different regime. so what can we do? i want to propose a new approach to an old idea, best this idea of image deconvolution. a star goes through the atmosphere, gets distorted, ground-based. but if you know the point spread function of sufficient accuracy you can remove the seeing versus deconvolution. in practice this is very hard to do because the background noise is there and you often end up deconvolving background noise and messing up your noise. as well as the spatial scales, you don't know if you are looking at a bright little source or more diffused faint source. and so it's always installed us with image deconvolution, have from working hard over the last decade coming up with better algorithms and an algorithm we've been working with his finite resolution deconvolution or firedec. instead of deconvolution to infinite resolution, you just deke involved slightly better. three or five times better than ground-based data and get rid of this high-frequency deconvolution noise that has always been a problem. the other even more important thing it does is using this new cost function analysis that separates signals from the object we want to deconvolve from the background noise we don't want to deconvolve. we are working with this now on cosmos and this is work by a phd student visal sok. the right as color images of galaxies in the cosmos, the left column is the ground-based data, the right is our deconvolve and on the right is hst data. it looks quite promising and in particular deconvolution noise is not overwhelming which has always been a problem in the past. here's just a zooming of one of them, this is typical for what we get. the ground faces on the left and you see a red and blue fuzzy blob. when we deconvolve you start to see a blue disk and red bulge, the hubble images on the right. you can see the deconvolution is not perfect and not as high resolution as hubble, however it is pretty good resolution and it's not -- it's significantly better than when you get with no deconvolution at all. this doesn't solve all your problems but if you use this in safe, careful ways, you can actually extract really interesting information. what he's working on is the fraction of galaxies with a star formation as a function of redshift, a lot of work has already been done on this with candels. red is low mass, blue is high mass. all the points in the background or work done with candels, we get results that are very consistent with the candels results which are based purely on space-based imaging but of course we are doing this from the ground. we reproduce the same normalization, we reproduce the same trend, you can see there's a slight difference in fraction of mass. and what i'm very impressed with is our aero bars, the candels studies have anywhere from about 200 to 800 galaxies and we've deconvolve 25,000 galaxies. you can see we have much, much smaller bars. well deconvolution is imperfect, i think it's used in careful ways it's really a promising way to learn things. we can think about the nancy roman grace high latitude survey, you are going to map 2,000 square degrees with ir imaging and for filters, may be more but at least four. and we've been talking about lsst and remain how it will cover the same survey was ground-based data. ground-based data is going to have very high signal-to-noise but it's going to have low spatial resolution. so what i would propose if there is an potential synergy here between using image deconvolution on the lsst data combined with higher resolution nancy roman and grace data to be able to make interesting stellar mass maps, star formation maps and all that kind of stuff for literally millions of galaxies. i think that's really exciting. andreea: 2 minutes. adam: perfect, let's talk quickly about star formation. nancy roman is going to be fantastic here but let's also talk about this girmos. girmos is a multi-object ifu, an analogy would be keck deimos. we are also going to do adaptive optics on those arms, and girmos is going to be the first science instrument to do multi-object adaptive optics. what that means is that every one of these ifu's is going to get its own deformable mirror and each one of them is going to have a correction that is optimized for its exact position in the field, you are going to get very high quality for each of the four objects that you select to do spectroscopy in the field. and we are very excited about girmos, we are in for luminary design right now. girmos we are hoping will be on the telescope in either late 2026 or early 2027. that's a great synergy timeline for nancy roman, because you can select objects that you are excited about and follow them up with girmos. so what can we do with girmos? the same kind of work that people have been doing with symphony, but in multi-object mode. this shows some work from forster or schreiber they've mapped out the metallicity, and in particular the kinematics. i think that's what's really exciting and that's what girmos adds to nancy roman data is well you will have beautiful grism observations that give you hl for maps, what we can do with girmos is kinematic information, we can do the dynamics of these galaxies and so i really see them coming along at the same time and really dovetailing with each other. so just to finish off, the census of taking properties of galaxies is almost over. we have to do results work for galaxies going forward. i think there's a really bright future for mapping stellar mass from space, but also

potentially with image deconvolution and i think girmos and other ifu spectrograph are going to be really exciting for mapping star formation in the distant universe in combination with nancy grace roman data. thank you for listening and bearing with my technical difficulties.

Andreea: thank you adam, thank you for rolling with the punches. there are several questions, so i will combine them. most about the firedec image deconvolution. is the firedec deconvolution limited to small spatial scale? or can we deconvolve the large wings of tss are greater than 3?

Adam: good question, i don't think we've tested that. the thing about deconvolution that you learn very quickly is it's all about signal-to-noise. the higher signal-to-noise you have, the higher signal-to-noise galaxies that you want to deconvolve, the better your deconvolution. while i haven't really tested wings and all of that stuff carefully, if you can -- deconvolution is exciting, what you really want to do is get beautiful bff that are very deep and beautiful imaging regardless of the image quality, and if you have both of those things in principle it should be able to. andreea: now in the section of what we need to watch out for and deconvolution methods, there's several questions. can you create artifacts in the image and if so, how do you manage to identify them? adam: that's a great question, that is always one of the problems with deconvolution is we have this -- firedec has this smoothing, it goes to find a resolution and tries to reduce that kind of artifact. you can't completely get rid of them but this is what i was referring to by using it carefully. member that we are deconvolve, we did the 15 best filters and you are feeling things like stellar mass. remember that all 15 images contribute to that. and so occasionally an artifact here or there in a filter or two will not ideal, kind of gets smoothed over by using the different wavelengths. that's what i'm referring to by using deconvolution carefully. if you use it at one wavelength it is dangerous, if you combine multiple you deal with the systematic artifacts and you can get out interesting properties. but you do have to be careful.

Andreea: we have one more question, and then go to the slack as possible. how does quality from your deconvolution techniques compare with modeling?

Adam: the thing is that forward modeling, the reason you want to use this and the reason that he's working on something galaxies is if you want to do parametric modeling, then forward modeling is the way to go. Why go backwards? deconvolution is degenerate, there's no point in going backwards. the only reason you want to go backwards with deconvolution if you want to do nonparametric things like for example measuring how clumping galaxies are. it's very difficult to forward model, you have infinite possible things you could forward model and that's where you would want to deconvolve.

Andreea: thank you very much, you do have more questions but we unfortunately have run out of time. and this concludes this session, i would like to think very much all the wonderful speakers and to wish you a great morning afternoon, and i will let you take it away.

Thank you Andreea for chairing this session, thank you to all the speakers of the session and thank you for attending the session. We will take about 15 minutes break and we will reconvene at 12:30 eastern time for our last session, session 10. See you in about 15 minutes. Thank you.

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